

INFORMING COMPONENTS DEVELOPMENT INNOVATIONS FOR FLOATING OFFSHORE WIND THROUGH APPLIED FMEA FRAMEWORK

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ABSTRACT

Future offshore wind technology solutions will be floating to facilitate deep water locations. The EUH2020 funded project FLOTANT (Innovative, low cost, low weight and safe floating wind technology optimized for deep water wind sites) aims to address the arising technical and economic challenges linked to this progress. In particular, innovative solutions in terms of mooring lines, power cable and floating platform, specifically designed for floating offshore wind devices, will be developed and tested, and the benefits provided by these components assessed. In this paper a purpose-built Failure Modes and Effect Analysis (FMEA) technique is presented, and applied to the novel floating offshore wind components. The aim is to determine the technology qualification, identify the key failure modes and assess the criticality of these components and their relative contributions to the reliability, availability and maintainability of the device. This will allow for the identification of suitable mitigation measures in the development lifecycle, as well as an assessment of potential cost savings and impacts of the specific innovations. The methodology takes into account inputs from the components developers and other project partners, as well as information extracted from existing literature and databases. Findings in terms of components innovations, their main criticalities and related mitigation measures, and impacts on preventive and corrective maintenance, will be presented in order to inform current and future developments for floating offshore wind devices.

Keywords: Floating offshore wind, FMEA, Criticality, Reliability, Floating platforms, Power cable, Moorings.

INTRODUCTION

The offshore wind sector is experiencing an incredible momentum, thanks to the substantial cost reductions in most of its development and exploitation related activities. Nonetheless,

bottom-fixed offshore wind installations are limited to shallow waters, generally less than 50m deep, in order to be economically and technically viable. In order to overcome this limitation and explore new sites, several upcoming projects are moving farther from the coast. These locations offer the advantage of being characterized by stronger and more stable wind regimes, offering the possibility of generating more energy. Due to the increased water depth, floating foundations will be needed to deploy the wind turbines. Therefore, a series of novel concepts for the successful installation and exploitation of floating offshore wind turbines (FOWT) will be needed.

It is in this context that the European Horizon 2020 project FLOTANT [1] (Innovative, low cost, low weight and safe floating wind technology optimized for deep water wind sites) is funded. The project involves 17 industrial and academic partners from across Europe, and will run for 36 months starting from April 2019. The main objective of FLOTANT is the development of innovative solutions to improve the robustness and cost-efficiency of 10+MW wind turbine generators in deep waters (100-600m). This goal will be achieved through the design and test of specific components, as well as the assessment and optimisation of the construction, installation, operation and decommissioning techniques, in line with state-of-the-art practices and environmental constraints. The components that will be designed and tested as part of the project are a hybrid plastic/concrete floating platform, a novel anchoring and mooring system, and a power export system. A graphic summary of the main FLOTANT innovations is illustrated in FIGURE 1.

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FIGURE 1: GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION OF FLOTANT OBJECTIVES [1].

Among other evaluations, an assessment of the operation and maintenance (O&M) expenses will be needed in order to estimate the lifecycle costs of the project and measure the contributions provided by FLOTANT innovations. To this end, a framework able to integrate corrective and preventive maintenance actions with the management of the maintenance assets [2], [3] will be exploited to characterize and optimize the O&M strategy. Besides, a network of sensors and communication protocols will be developed to monitor and control the functioning of the device. As a result, proactive and predictive maintenance strategies able to reduce failures and downtime of the floating devices will be produced.

In order to facilitate these tasks, i.e. inform choice of sensors and maintenance plans, a Failure Modes and Effect Analysis (FMEA) methodology is presented in this paper. This is based on the inputs from the components' developers and existing literature, and is used in order to understand and improve the contribution of FLOTANT novel components to system reliability and maintenance planning.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In section 1.1 the novel components developed for FLOTANT are presented. In section 2, the FMEA methodology specifically developed for the objectives of this work is described. Thus, an overview of the results obtained through application of the adapted FMEA framework is provided in section 3. Finally, the implications of these outcomes on the maintenance planning and components development are discussed in section 4, and conclusions drawn in section 5.

1.1 FLOTANT innovative components

The integrated solution for FOWT proposed by FLOTANT is based on three main innovations, holistically conceived and hereinafter described.

The first one is a mooring system based on the use of high performance and lightweight fibres and elastomers. Each

mooring cable consists of multiple hybrid polymer carbon fibre rods, embedded in a thermoplastic epoxy matrix which maximizes the anti-bite and anti-fouling resistance. A sample of an ultra-high strength (200 Tones MWL) cable section is shown in FIGURE 2. The mooring cables are complemented by polymer springs, to reduce peak loads, and an anchoring system equipped with active heave compensation. This last is used in order to vary the length of each mooring line depending on platform motions in response to external loads. To measure these, sensing solutions in terms of optic fibres for the mooring cable and acoustic or optical sensors for the polymer springs, will be integrated. A wide range of moorings and anchors configurations has been explored in order to find the optimal solution for the station-keeping of the FOWT, and taking a series of water depths and metocean conditions into account.

The second innovation focuses on a dynamic power cable and export system engineered with a specific view on deep water scenarios. The cable, graphically represented in the render in FIGURE 3, is rated at 72.5 kV, according to current standards for windfarms applications. However, the main novelty consists in choosing an XLPE insulated core with an Aluminum conductor (instead of a copper) in order to reduce weight (and cost), and therefore improve the response and load behavior of the cable. This choice affects the cable core cross section dimensioning, as well as its dynamic properties. The marine power cable design criteria, with a view on performance and reliability assessments, are provided in [4]. A full assessment of the mechanical performance and load parameters for an Aluminum power conductor cable for FOWT applications is provided in [5]. The insulate cable core is currently being tested in a saline solution under AC voltage for a total period of two years in order to verify its ageing properties. A novel synthetic armour is considered as a strength member for the submarine cable applied in form of braid (instead of steel wire armour) to provide lower weight and extra flexibility. An enhanced extruded outer jacket, including addition of short synthetic fibres, is developed in order to provide appropriate mechanical robustness, bending and torsion stiffness to the cable. Anti-fouling and anti-bite additives are added for additional protection. A mechanical hang-off and emergency breakaway system is developed in conjunction with the power cable in order to facilitate and speed up plug and play operations. This includes fast-coupling wet-mate connectors at the interface between cable and platform.

FIGURE 2: SAMPLE OF FLOTANT ULTRA-HIGH STRENGTH CABLE SECTION SHOWING RODS BUNDLE, RESIN CONE AND CABLE FIXED CONNECTOR. COURTESY OF FUTURE FIBRES LTD.

The third innovation consists in the design of a floating platform capable of hosting 10+MW wind turbines. This is self-buoyant and self-stable semisubmersible foundation having a diameter of 80m, made principally of concrete in order to reduce life-cycle costs and increase resistance to degradation, with elements of steel embedded to provide reinforcement to the structure. Flexible, plastic-coated, reinforced bags are included within the base of the platform in order to provide it the required buoyancy at a lower cost. The bags can be filled with air in order to reduce the draught of the platform up to 12m, e.g. at port or during towing operations, and then filled with water once on site in order to ballast the device and increase the draught up to the desired level (max 35m). This active ballast system, employing pumps to move water between adjacent plastic compartments, is also used for control of the whole platform, in order to counteract tilting moments due to wind. A scheme of FLOTANT platform is shown in FIGURE 4.

These three innovations are coupled to each other, and their performance will be evaluated considering the overall system and including considerations on costs and operational procedures.

FIGURE 3: RENDERING OF FLOTANT 72.5 KV DYNAMIC SUBMARINE CABLE. COURTESY OF FULGOR S.A.

FIGURE 4: SCHEME OF FLOTANT PLATFORM. COURTESY OF ESTEYCO S.A.

METHODOLOGY

An approach based on the Failure Modes and Effect Analysis (FMEA) technique, but specifically adjusted for the assessment of novel floating offshore wind components according to industry best practices, is chosen for this work. The FMEA is a standard procedure, widely used in several industries, aiming at increasing reliability and maintainability of a system. The analysis is generally carried out during the early-stage of a project development, e.g. initial planning and design, and then regularly updated at later stages. The procedure is commonly divided in sequential steps, with the purpose of identifying the potential failure modes of a system, together with their potential impacts, and find suitable mitigation measures to prevent or reduce their consequences. As a result the areas of major risk are highlighted, potential negative effects minimized and useful indications for the improvements of the system’s maintainability are derived. The basic principles and definitions of the FMEA methodology can be found in several international standards, e.g. IEC 60812:2006 [6], MIL-STD-1629A [7] and BS 5760-5:1991 [8]. However, the methodology can be adjusted according to the

context and objectives of each specific project. In this work, the main purposes of conducting an FMEA analysis on FLOTANT innovations are:

- Identifying solution for the improvement of novel components design;
- Informing choice of sensors and condition monitoring instrumentation; and
- Informing the choice of suitable assets and procedures for safe and cost-effective maintenance.

The FMEA methodology was organized in the following way. Firstly, an ad-hoc framework to achieve the above goals was created according to indications from literature and FLOTANT innovations’ features. This was distributed among component developers, who provided a first assessment according to their expertise and innovation development plans. Thus, the resulting worksheet was revised by experts and other relevant partners, who provided their feedback, and component developers were consulted individually to solve eventual doubts and open questions. A workshop involving all relevant stakeholders was then organized to ensure completeness, as well as coherency and consistency, throughout the framework.

The steps of the FMEA framework, specifically developed for the innovative concepts introduced with FLOTANT, are hereinafter described and graphically summarized in FIGURE 5.

1) Produce taxonomy of the components

A preliminary step consisted in establishing a suitable structure that would facilitate the identification and organization of relevant items within FLOTANT innovations. Thus, a suitable taxonomy structure has been defined according to previous studies for the wind and tidal energy sectors [9]–[11]. To delineate the boundaries of the system at a sufficient level of detail for the scopes of the analysis, a taxonomy based on the following hierarchy is established:

However, for the sake of simplicity and unless distinction is required, the identified items in the various taxonomies are generically indicated as ‘components’ throughout the rest of this study. The taxonomy of the three FLOTANT innovations analyzed in this work is presented in Tables 1 - 3.

TABLE 1: FLOTANT MOORING SYSTEM TAXONOMY.

Mooring system				
Subsystem	Assembly	Component	Subcomponent	
Mooring Spring	Polymer Spring	polymer shells		
		welded joints		
	Metal Sub-structure	Assembly (x2)		Beams
				Metal Plate
				Anti-corrosion paint
				Bearings
				Pad-eye
		Sacrificial anodes		
	Fibre Rope	Mooring cable	Pultruded rods	Structural rod
				Functional rod
Enveloping braid				
Coating				
Lower End Fittings (anchor end)			Fixed conector	
			Removal Interface	
Upper End Fittings (platform end)			Fixed conector	
			Removal Interface	
Load monitoring sensor			Sensor	
			Connector	
Active compensation system	Hydraulic/electric winch	Hydromotor		
		Electric motor		
		Gearbox		
	Hydraulic cylinder	Hydraulic cylinder		
		Speed sensor		
		Position sensors		
	Hydraulic power unit	El.motor		
		Hydraulic pump		
		Valves		
	Hydro accumulator			
	Sensing and monitoring unit	Accelerometer		
		Gyroscope sensors		

TABLE 2: FLOTANT POWER CABLE TAXONOMY.

Power cable		
Subsystem	Assembly	Component
Submarine Power Cable System	Dynamic Power Cable	Enhanced extruded outer jacket
		armour braid
		Laid up cores
		Insulated core
		Dynamic power cable strength members
	Hang Off Breakaway system	Internal mechanical strain termination
		External mechanical locking mechanism
		Electrical connectors
		Fibre optic connectors

2) *Identify and characterize possible failure modes*

After identifying all the relevant elements of the subsystems investigated in this work, their function is defined in order to support the understanding of the system and the identification of possible failure modes. A failure mode is defined as the way in which a certain element can fail to comply with its expected or required function. In other words, it indicates how a failure occurs and is observed. Therefore, also the way in which each failure mode can be detected is assessed, together with the most likely root cause which initiates the failure. When failure modes are analyzed, the following factors should be taken into account for each item: drawings and description; material specifications; fabrication, installation and maintenance procedures. Since the FMEA is constructed on the assumption that each considered item can fail only in a certain way at a time, different failures modes for the same component (jointly with their respective root cause and detection manner) have to be identified and addressed separately. A last requirement for this step is the valuation of whether the consequences of the failure are limited to the component under examination or have repercussion on the entire system or subsystem. In both cases, eventual effects on the power production (e.g. partial or total loss of capacity with respect to the rated power) have also to be evaluated. Pre-determined

production classes, indicating the extent to which the electricity generation is affected (including catastrophic consequences on the whole system), are used for this scope.

TABLE 3: FLOTANT FLOATING PLATFORM TAXONOMY.

Floating platform			
Subsystem	Assembly	Component	Subcomponent
Tower	Steel tower	Top flange	Bolts
			Steel flange
		Sheet	
		Bottom flange	Steel flange
			Bolts
	Door		
	Concrete tower	Top flange	
		Access platform	
		Body	
		Ladder	
		Bottom joint	
Base	Plastic compartments	Compartments	
		Anchoring	
	Concrete wall	Wall	
		Mooring anchoring	
		Boat landing	Structure
	Ladder		
	Bulkheads		
	Concrete cylinder		
	Concrete slab	Slab	
		Heave plate	

3) Assess criticality of failure modes

Once all relevant failure modes have been identified and included in the FMEA worksheet, their criticality is assessed in terms of their severity, likelihood of occurrence, and probability of detection. Classes for each of these categories are adapted from previous literature [7], [9-10] as shown in Tables 4 - 6, and a score in a scale 1-10 is given to each failure mode accordingly. The severity is intended as the possible impacts of a failure on safety, the environment, operation of the device, and costs. Five classes with various degree of severity are used to assign the score. When a failure mode causes consequences with respect to more than one category (e.g. operation and safety) the highest score among those that can be applied is selected. The likelihood of occurrence is divided in five classes depending on expected event frequency (i.e. indicative failure rate). Similarly, probability of detection is divided in four classes depending on the expected likelihood of detecting the failure with current monitoring methods. It must be noted that the criterion to assign a score to the probability of detection is the opposite than the previous two, i.e. the more likely is the detection of the failure the lower will be the corresponding score.

TABLE 4: SEVERITY CLASSES USED.

Severity Classes					
Score	Description of consequences (impact on)				
	Safety	Environment	Operation	Assets	Cost [€]
1 - 2	Negligible injury, effect on health	Negligible pollution or no effect	Negligible effect on production	Negligible	1k
3 - 4	Minor injuries, health effects	Minor pollution/slight effect (minimum disruption on marine life)	Partial loss of performance	Repairable within maintenance interval	10k
5 - 6	Moderate injuries and/or health effects	Limited levels of pollution, manageable / moderate effect	Loss of performance requiring retrieval	Repairable outside maintenance interval	100k
7 - 8	Significant injuries	Moderate pollution with clean-up costs / Serious effect	Total loss of production up to 1 month	Significant but repairable outside maintenance interval	1m
9 - 10	A fatality	Major pollution with significant clean-up costs / disastrous effects	Total loss of production greater than 1 month	Loss of device, major repair needed by removal of device and exchange of major components	10m

TABLE 5: LIKELIHOOD CLASSES USED.

Likelihood Classes			
Score	Name	Description	Indicative Annual Failure Rate (up to)
1 - 2	Very Low	Negligible event frequency	0.0001
3 - 4	Low	Event unlikely to occur	0.001
5 - 6	Medium	Event rarely expected to occur	0.01
7 - 8	High	One or several events expected to occur during the lifetime	0.1
9 - 10	Very high	One or several events expected to occur each year	1

TABLE 6: DETECTION CLASSES USED.

Detection Classes		
Score	Description	Criteria
1 - 2	Almost certain	Current monitoring methods almost always detect the failure
3 - 5	High	Good likelihood current monitoring methods will detect the failure
6 - 8	Low	Low likelihood current monitoring methods will detect the failure
9 - 10	Almost impossible	No known monitoring methods available to detect the failure or destructive testing needed to detect it

Once severity, likelihood and detections are assessed independently, the scores assigned to the three classes are multiplied in order to obtain the so-called Risk Priority Number (RPN), which provides a quantitative measure of the risk related to each failure mode. A risk matrix is then defined in order to obtain a qualitative measure of the risk (e.g. low, medium or high), which provides an indicator of the urgency and type of mitigation. The same criteria described in [10] was used to link RPN to qualitative risk: Low if $RPN \leq 63$; Medium if $64 \leq RPN \leq 125$; High if $RPN \geq 126$.

4) Propose mitigation measures

At this point, a clear understanding of what kind of issues may arise in the functioning of each component, together with corresponding root causes and detection methods, has been obtained. Therefore it is necessary to propose actions or activities that can reduce the negative impacts or the likelihood of the failure, or alternatively that can increase its chances or ease of detection. These can include recommendations for a revised design of the component, the inclusion of monitoring instrumentation, the proposal of maintenance actions targeted for the specific failure mode under consideration, and permanent or temporary arrangements of other kinds (e.g. redundancy measures). When these mitigating actions are proposed, cost and practicality of each solution should be taken into account. For example, maintenance actions offshore requiring significant workforce and expensive assets should be avoided in favor of permanent arrangements which increase the reliability of the system and reduce the need of manned intervention.

5) Revise criticality of failure modes

The last step consists in re-evaluating the criticality of the failure modes in light of the identified mitigation measures. In this way the effectiveness of the proposed measures can be assessed, and, most importantly, any outstanding actions in order to further reduce risk recognized.

FIGURE 5: FLOTANT FMEA METHODOLOGY.

RESULTS

The main outcomes and observations of the FMEA framework applied to FLOTANT innovations are provided in this section. As already mentioned, the analysis was conducted on three main subsystems: mooring arrangement, power cable and floating platform. However, since it is part of the load path (and this must be taken into account for the basis design), also the steel tower was considered as part of the FMEA on the floating platform.

From a first overview of the results, the subsystem with the highest number of criticalities is the mooring system. However, this can be explained by the fact which is also the subsystem with the highest number of identified components and failure modes. Nonetheless, risks for the mooring system (including potential

TABLE 7: SUMMARY OF RESULTS FROM FMEA ON FLOTANT INNOVATIONS.

System	Identified components	Identified failure modes	Criticalities before mitigation			Criticalities after mitigation			Impact		Effect on power production			
			Low	Medium	High	Low	Medium	High	Local	System	None	Partial	Total	Catastrophic
Mooring system	21	42	13	18	11	31	11	0	12	29	28	9	0	4
Power cable	9	17	2	9	6	13	4	0	6	11	3	8	2	4
Floating platform	23	29	23	5	1	29	0	0	13	16	6	7	6	10
Total	53	88	38	32	18	73	15	0	31	56	37	24	8	18

catastrophic failures due to fracture of the mooring cable fittings) are effectively alleviated when mitigation measures are taken into account and the criticality is revised. On the contrary, the floating platform results being the most reliable system (i.e. lowest number of high and medium risk failure modes), but also the one with the highest number of potentially catastrophic failure modes or having potential impacts on the entire device. This is understandable considering that failures of the platform or the tower would cause significant impact on the device and the surrounding environment. The power cable presents a sort of intermediate situation, with a number of failure modes at low to medium risk which can be easily reduced with the proposed mitigation measures, as well as four potentially catastrophic failure modes (the break or damage of armor braid, aluminum conductor, strain termination and electrical connectors) which can be mitigated with the identified measures but also need further investigation in order to be properly managed. Interestingly, this is also the subsystem with the highest number of failure modes (e.g. break or damage of aluminum conductor or fiber Bragg grating (FBG) units) whose root causes can be related to installation and maintenance procedures. Thus, the specifics of the FMEA will provide essential information for the planning of these procedure.

When the results of the FMEA are analyzed more in detail, a series of observation can be made. A total of 53 components were identified and subdivided according to the proposed taxonomy structuration. For these components, a total of 88 possible failure modes were recognized. In terms of criticality, 18 of these were classified at high risk, 32 at medium risk and 38 at low risk. A summary of these outcomes is provided in Table 7. The most common failure modes were:

- for the mooring system and its components: fracture, excessive deformation, wear, impact, weld failure, wrong systems adjustment;
- for the power cable and its components: excessive biomass growth, overheating, mechanical damage, deterioration; and
- for the floating platform and its components: bolt breaking, nut loosening, steel deformation, welding failure, and cracking or breaking.

The most common root causes responsible for the occurrence of these failure modes were:

- for the mooring system and its components: fatigue, overload, wear, corrosion;
- for the power cable and its components: fatigue, insulation deterioration, inadequate outer jacket additives, abrasion, installation and maintenance activities;
- for the floating platform and its components: excessive load or vibration, incorrect welding, inappropriate tightening, corrosion.

In response to the identified failure modes, suitable mitigation measures were proposed. In this regard, failure modes with medium or high risk were given priority in the search for suitable mitigation measures. Among these, the most common recommendations (in terms of redesign, monitoring or maintenance practices) to reduce criticality (either by reducing severity and/or likelihood, or by increasing ease of detection), were:

- for the mooring system and its components: use of established methodologies (e.g. finite element analysis (FEA)) to ensure design to requirements, adoption of standards and certifications guidelines, regular inspections and repairs;
- for the power cable and its components: long term insulation aging tests, extensive fatigue, strain, production and integrity tests; distributed temperature sensing (DTS), fibre optics and fibre Bragg grating (FBG); regular inspections and biomass removal;
- for the floating platform and its components: accidental load state (ALS) analysis to assess damaged conditions, the use of stress gauges and inclinometers, and visual inspections.

When all the mitigation measures are taken into account there are not components left with high criticality; the remaining ones are 15 at medium and 73 at low risk.

DISCUSSION

The outcomes of the FMEA are based on the expertise and previous experience of the project partners who contributed to its construction. As such, results may be biased by individual knowledge and amendable for improvement. However, the

results show that if sufficient awareness on a series of factors is raised since the early stage of the design process, risks in the component development can be effectively mitigated. These factors include, but are not limited to: established design methodologies, adoption of international standards and industry best practices, knowledge of manufacture and supply procedures, and consideration of installation and maintenance practices. Hence, these results provide precious assistance in the so-called design for reliability (DFR), which aims at reducing servicing costs by implementing sound decisions before physical prototyping of the components. Similarly, important indications to support manufacturers in fabricating defect-free components, as well as to assist service managers in planning installation and operations, are obtained with this work.

Despite the preliminary intention of avoiding maintenance interventions when possible, regular inspections have been among the most proposed maintenance recommendations. However, the exact time interval between consecutive visual or sensors-aided inspections has not been provided. Following discussion with component developers these are not easily determinable. Therefore, appropriate intervals for inspections will have to be defined, using models for the long-term planning of O&M strategies like those mentioned in the introduction. For this purpose, the information provided with the FMEA will be used in conjunction with previous literature and databases to establish the reliability inputs for the simulations. This, in turn will then be used to establish service requirements, both under warranty and beyond, and negotiate with O&M contractors.

Moreover, the results of this FMEA will assist the SCADA and Condition monitoring implementation, which will aid the definition of the optimal condition-based aspects of maintenance. As a result, the choice of sensors and condition monitoring instrumentation, useful to detect in advance any degradation or deviation from operational conditions of the novel components, will be informed and based on these outcomes. At the same time, the necessary adjustments in order to consider adequately their integration in the taxonomy of the device, and consequent O&M modelling and strategy planning, will be derived. These processes are fundamental in order to reduce uncertainties in the quest towards the optimal life-cycle maintenance plan. In this regard, a further innovation may be provided by the implementation of so-called soft (or virtual) sensors [14]. These are data or model driven predictive techniques which constitute a valid alternative to traditional monitoring and control instruments. The principle is that response variables of interest can be estimated and predicted based on the information obtained through instrumentation installed elsewhere in a cheaper or easier way. For example, in the case of FLOTANT components, it could be possible to compute mooring cable and/or power cable stresses based on the motions of the floating platform, avoiding the installation of more sensitive instrumentation on the cables themselves.

Despite these benefits, the methodology presents some shortcomings. For example, interconnected or cascading failure modes, due to failure of a subsystem different than the one considered or to extreme events with chain reactions, are not well

captured. Besides, identical failures for the same components might cause different effects depending on which device they happen. For example, the failure of the power cable on the first device of the array might cause the loss of generation for the whole array, as opposed to the same failure in the last device of the array that would not affect the other ones. These cases should also be distinguished and assessed in the framework.

Again, the practical and economical feasibility of the proposed mitigation measures has not been investigated in this framework. This means that all the re-design, condition monitoring, and preventive maintenance interventions suggested will have to be weighed against their feasibility of implementation and added cost, and a decision on whether to accept them or not made. Similarly, other factors such as logistical or technical constraints, as well as weather related effects, have not been fully integrated at this stage.

In light of these observations, more than as a final output this work can be considered as a fundamental starting point, aiming at successfully supporting the sensors selection and the setup of O&M models. In fact, in order to be fully effective, it is paramount that the FMEA is implemented at the very early stage of a project, when changes and modifications to preliminary designs can be easily made without drastically affecting the overall development process. Subsequently, a structural design process, considering the loads and responses in components estimated by means of specific numerical models, will be used to analyze the final designs and make sure that they respect the desired reliability requirements. As such, structural design will be complimentary to the FMEA analysis. Finally, early implementation of these processes permits to reduce efforts (and costs) on the future O&M of the device.

CONCLUSIONS

The implementation of the FMEA on FLOTANT innovations has allowed the consortium to achieve a full understanding of the components under development, with a particular emphasis on their reliability and maintainability. The methodology has permitted the identification of the main weaknesses and potential risks of the systems under investigation, as well as that of the elements and components that are worth being further examined or improved. The framework takes into account inputs from the components developers and other project partners, as well as information extracted from existing literature and databases. In this way, potential failure modes are assessed, their likely causes identified and associated risks and consequences acknowledged. Consequently, the criticality of the components is estimated, and a set of suitable mitigation measures proposed. These last are provided in terms of design or manufacturing improvements, suggested test or monitoring actions, appropriate maintenance assets and preventive maintenance recommendations, with the intent to reduce the likelihood and limit the consequences of possible failures.

As such, this work constitutes a useful reference for current and future FOWT developers, providing a summary of possible issues and corresponding mitigation measures for the main

components of a floating device. Besides, it will facilitate the comparison against traditional bottom fixed offshore wind devices, highlighting main advantages and drawbacks of floating solutions and hence aiding the economic assessment of this novel offshore renewable sector.

Future work will consist in joining the results of this work with other risk management techniques, considering other information and parameters which will allow a more informed assessment and subsequent decision-making. This will aid the structural design and more general technology development, and reduce exposure to risks. Besides, the FMEA will be kept up to date, according to the progresses in the development and test activities of the various components or as more data and information become available. Thus, design recommendations will be updated and the simulations exploiting O&M models to inform the strategic planning of the FOWT repeated.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the project "FLOTANT", grant agreement number 815289.

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